

Complicated Waldeyer's Hernia: A Rare Cause of Acute Small Bowel Obstruction

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Abstract

Paraduodenal hernias are rare congenital internal hernias resulting from abnormal midgut rotation. They represent the most common type of internal hernia but remain a rare cause of small bowel obstruction. The right-sided form is particularly uncommon. We report a 64-year-old man with no significant past medical history presenting with bowel obstruction for 4 days. CT scan showed a right paraduodenal hernia extending to the right iliac fossa, containing the terminal ileum, appendix, and several ileal loops arranged in a sac-like configuration. Surgery confirmed a right paraduodenal hernia containing viable small bowel from the fourth jejunal to the terminal ileal loop. Reduction and closure of the defect were performed. Postoperative recovery was uneventful. Right paraduodenal hernia results from abnormal midgut rotation. Preoperative diagnosis remains challenging, but CT imaging is crucial. Surgical reduction and closure of the defect provide excellent outcomes. Right paraduodenal hernia should be considered in unexplained small bowel obstruction without a surgical history. Early diagnosis and prompt surgery ensure favourable outcomes.

Keywords: Right Paraduodenal Hernia, Small Bowel Obstruction, Surgery.

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Introduction

Internal hernias are a rare cause of small bowel obstruction (0.2–0.9% of cases). Among these, paraduodenal hernias are the most frequent. Two types exist: left (Lanzert) and right (Waldeyer). The right paraduodenal hernia (RPDH) is rarer [1] and represents about 25% of all PDHs. Because symptoms are nonspecific, diagnosis is often delayed or made intraoperatively. Modern CT imaging has improved preoperative recognition. We present a case of right paraduodenal hernia revealed by small bowel obstruction and discuss diagnostic and therapeutic aspects with a literature review.

Case Presentation

A 64-year-old man with no medical history presented with a 4-day history of bowel obstruction (no stool/gas passage, abdominal distension, and food vomiting). He was afebrile with preserved general condition. On examination, the abdomen was distended with periumbilical tympanism; the digital rectal exam was normal. CT scan (figure 1) showed jejunal and ileal dilatation (up to 38 mm) upstream of a right paraduodenal hernia extending to the right iliac fossa, containing the terminal ileum, appendix, and several ileal loops in

a C-shaped configuration. Mild congestion and fat stranding were noted. The cecum was normally located.

Figure 1: CT Scan Showing Paraduodenal hernia and Transition Point

Surgery (figure 2) confirmed right paraduodenal hernia type B containing viable small bowel (from 4th jejunal to terminal ileal loop). Reduction and defect closure were performed. Recovery was uneventful; discharge on postoperative day 2.

Figure 2: Intraoperative view revealing hernia sac containing small bowel loops with proximal bowel distension

Discussion

Right paraduodenal hernia (RPDH) is a rare congenital anomaly resulting from abnormal rotation and fixation of the midgut during embryologic development. Normally, the midgut undergoes a 270° counterclockwise rotation around the superior mesenteric artery (SMA). When this process is incomplete, a potential space known as Waldeyer's fossa persists behind the SMA and the inferior mesenteric vein, allowing small bowel loops to herniate into the right mesocolon. This defect gives rise to a right paraduodenal hernia, which accounts for approximately 25% of all paraduodenal hernias, themselves being the most common type of internal hernia [1,2].

Clinically, the RPDH may remain silent for years. In most cases, it is discovered in its complicated form, presenting as acute small bowel obstruction characterized by abdominal distension, vomiting, and cessation of stool or gas passage [3,4]. Because of its rarity and lack of specific clinical features, diagnosis is often delayed or made incidentally during surgery [5].

Abdominopelvic CT remains the gold standard for diagnosis of RPDH. Typically demonstrating: a cluster of small bowel loops located in the right upper or mid-abdomen, often forming a C-shaped configuration with displacement of the mesenteric vessels and a normally positioned cecum [6-7].

The surgical treatment is the cornerstone of management. The procedure involves gentle reduction of herniated loops and closure or widening of the hernial orifice to prevent recurrence or vascular injury. When bowel viability is compromised, resection with primary

anastomosis is indicated [8-9]. Although traditionally performed via laparotomy, laparoscopic repair has become increasingly reported in recent years, providing reduced postoperative pain, faster recovery, and shorter hospital stay without compromising safety [10-11].

Conclusion

Right paraduodenal (Waldeyer's) hernia is a rare congenital internal hernia that is often discovered in a complicated form, usually presenting as acute small bowel obstruction. Early recognition, especially with CT imaging, is crucial for timely diagnosis and prevention of strangulation. Surgical procedure, whether open or laparoscopic, is the definitive treatment. Gentle reduction of herniated loops and secure closure of the hernial orifice ensure excellent outcomes.

Databases consulted

A systematic literature search was performed in PubMed, Embase, and Scopus using the following MeSH and free-text terms: ("Hernia, Internal" OR "internal hernia") AND ("right paraduodenal hernia" OR "Waldeyer hernia"). The search was limited to human studies published between 2015 and 2025 in English or French.

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